

Notes

Preparation and Characterisation of Adducts of Hexamethylphosphoramide with Copper(II) Carboxylates

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HEXAMETHYLPHOSPHORAMIDE (HMPA) has four donor sites (three nitrogen atoms and one oxygen atom) but it invariably acts as a unidentate oxygen donor molecule. It forms coordination compounds with a large variety of organic compounds, Lewis acids and inorganic salts¹. However, no work is reported on its complexes with copper(II) carboxylates except the one describing its complex with copper(II) chloroacetate². This prompted us to investigate its complexes with some of the copper(II) carboxylates.

Experimental

Carboxylic acids (B.D.H.), $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (AnalaR) and HMPA (B.D.H.) were used as such. Basic CuCO_3 , $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (B.D.H.) was purified by washing with hot water. Solvents were purified by conventional methods. Copper(II) arylcarboxylates and chloroacetates were prepared by standard methods^{3,4}.

Complexes were prepared by the interaction of equimolar quantities of the requisite amounts of copper(II) carboxylates and the ligand in an appropriate organic solvent with or without refluxing. The reaction mixture on concentration deposited the desired products which were separated, washed with appropriate solvents like acetone and methanol, and dried over calcium chloride at room temperature. In some cases, the product obtained was recrystallised from a suitable organic solvent, such as methanol before drying.

Copper was estimated gravimetrically as cuprous thiocyanate. Carbon and hydrogen were determined in the Microanalytical Laboratory of this department. Molar conductance was determined on millimolar solutions in 1,4-dioxane and methanol using Elico CM 82T conductivity bridge and a conductivity cell with a cell constant of 0.50. Magnetic moments were determined by Gouy's method. Electronic spectra were scanned on a Beckman-DB spectrophotometer in chloroform. Diffuse reflectance spectra were recorded on a Carl-

Zeiss DMR-21 ultraviolet, visible and near-infrared spectrophotometer. Ir spectra were recorded on a Pye Unicam SP 2000 spectrophotometer in KBr.

Results and Discussion

The complexes isolated are green crystalline compounds of 1 : 1 stoichiometry as shown by their elemental analysis (Table 1). The complexes are slightly hygroscopic and dissolve in common organic solvents giving solutions which decompose on prolonged standing. Cryoscopic molecular weight studies on these systems did not afford satisfactory results because of their insufficient solubility in benzene and nitrobenzene. The molar conductance values which lie in the range 0.025-0.624 and 18.11-85.20 $\text{mol}^{-1} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2$ in 1,4-dioxane and methanol, respectively suggest that the complexes are non-ionic in nature^{5,6}.

The magnetic moment values of these complexes fall in the range 1.46-1.63 B.M. at room temperature (Table 1) and are similar to those of dimeric carboxylate bridged mono-adducts of copper(II) carboxylates with other oxygen donors⁷. This suggests that these complexes also have a carboxylate bridged structure similar to that of copper(II) acetate monohydrate⁸. The magnetic moment values of the present complexes are somewhat higher than those of 1.30-1.45 B.M. observed for typical dimeric adducts of copper(II) carboxylates⁹. This may be attributed to high steric requirements of the ligand which somehow cause a reduction in the magnetic exchange occurring in these systems thereby making them to acquire comparatively higher magnetic moments.

The solution and diffuse electronic spectra of the complexes show one broad band lying between 675 and 728 nm excepting copper(II) dichloroacetate adduct which shows this band at 800 nm in its diffuse reflectance spectra. This band is a characteristic of blue or green copper(II) complexes having a distorted octahedral stereochemistry and is assigned to the $d_{xy, yz} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ transition¹⁰. However, the 2nd band which appears as a shoulder around 375 nm in many dimeric complexes of copper(II) carboxylates¹¹ is missing in the spectra of these complexes. Since a number of non-dimeric complexes have also been found to exhibit this band¹², its presence cannot be regarded as a diagnostic feature of dimeric structure. Hence, its absence in the present complexes does not preclude the possibility that they are dimeric.

In the infrared spectra the $\nu_{P=O}$ of the complexes exhibits a negative shift of 85-138 cm^{-1} as compared to the corresponding frequency of the ligand² suggesting that HMPA coordinates through its oxygen atom to the metal ion in these systems^{2,13}. The

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, MAGNETIC AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF HMPA COMPLEXES OF COPPER(II) CARBOXYLATES

Sl no.	Compd.	M. p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			λ_{max} nm	μ_{eff} B.M.
			Cu	C	H		
1.	Cu(benzoate) ₂ .HMPA	238*	12.89 (13.11)	49.38 (49.53)	5.59 (5.77)	700 ^a	1.52
2.	Cu(<i>o</i> -methylbenzoate) ₂ .HMPA	226	12.17 (12.39)	51.26 (51.51)	6.12 (6.24)	680 ^b	1.59
3.	Cu(<i>m</i> -methylbenzoate) ₂ .HMPA	*	12.20 (12.39)	51.29 (51.51)	6.19 (6.24)	690 ^b	1.63
4.	Cu(<i>p</i> -methylbenzoate) ₂ .HMPA	247	12.27 (12.39)	51.30 (51.51)	6.09 (6.24)	682 ^a	1.46
5.	Cu(<i>o</i> -chlorobenzoate) ₂ .HMPA	214	11.27 (11.47)	43.17 (43.36)	4.48 (4.69)	685 ^a	1.60
6.	Cu(<i>m</i> -chlorobenzoate) ₂ .HMPA	249	11.39 (11.47)	43.19 (43.36)	4.50 (4.69)	680 ^b	1.56
7.	Cu(<i>p</i> -methoxybenzoate) ₂ .HMPA	241	11.40 (11.66)	48.27 (48.48)	5.68 (5.87)	675 ^a	1.50
8.	Cu(<i>m</i> -nitrobenzoate) ₂ .HMPA	248	10.92 (11.06)	41.56 (41.77)	4.41 (4.52)	685 ^a	1.48
9.	Cu(monochloroacetate) ₂ .HMPA	188	14.32 (14.79)	27.68 (27.93)	5.01 (5.12)	690 ^a 716 ^b	1.56
10.	Cu(dichloroacetate) ₂ .HMPA	202*	12.58 (12.74)	23.88 (24.07)	3.88 (4.01)	800 ^a 728 ^b	1.63

*Decomposes. ^aDiffuse reflectance spectra. ^bIn CHCl₃.

frequency difference between the asymmetric and symmetric carboxylate stretches lies in the range 230-250 cm⁻¹ with the exception of the complex of copper(II) dichloroacetate where this separation is 286 cm⁻¹. These values are appreciably higher than those found in the corresponding parent copper(II) carboxylates and are similar to those of binuclear complexes of copper(II) arylcarboxylates and chloroacetates with oxygen donors¹⁴ suggesting a usual dimeric carboxylate bridged structure for these complexes.

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Studies on some Mixed Ligand Complexes of Copper(II) and Nickel(II) Pyrrolidonates with some Nitrogen Donors

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A large number of transition metal complexes with various heterocyclic Schiff bases and oximes have been reported from this laboratory¹⁻⁵. The present paper reports the studies on some mixed ligand complexes of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} pyrrolidonates with different amines, such as aniline piperidine, α -picoline, pyridine (L), ethylenediamine, tetramethylethylenediamine (L') and diethylenetriamine or triethylenetetraamine (L'').